

An Ethnobotanical Investigation Of Medicinal Plants Used Among Rural And Tribal Communities For The Treatment Of Febrile Illnesses In Sohelwa Wildlife Sanctuary And Its Adjoining Areas

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Abstract:

Traditional herbal home remedies play a vital role in primary healthcare among rural and tribal communities in India. The present study aims to document the knowledge and use of medicinal plants for the treatment of febrile illnesses among households in the Sohelwa Wildlife Sanctuary and its adjoining areas of the Tarai region of Uttar Pradesh, India. Ethnobotanical data were collected through structured interviews, household surveys, and focus group discussions using a standardized questionnaire to ensure diverse community representation. Plant specimens were collected, processed, and identified using standard floras and reference literature. The study recorded 48 ethnobotanical plant species representing 44 genera and belonging to 27 families that are traditionally used to treat various fever conditions. Fabaceae emerged as the most dominant plant family, with five species. The continued reliance on herbal remedies highlights the importance of traditional knowledge systems, particularly in regions with limited access to modern healthcare. Documentation of such ethnomedicinal practices is essential for the conservation of indigenous knowledge and may contribute to future pharmacological research.

Key words: Ethnomedicinal plants, indigenous communities, febrile illnesses, Sohelwa Wildlife Sanctuary.

1. Introduction

Medicinal plants have historically constituted the principal basis of health care systems worldwide (Gerique, 2006). Established traditional medical systems, including Ayurveda in India, Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) in China, and Muti in Africa, have been embedded within their respective cultural frameworks for several centuries (Singh *et al.* 2023). Angiospermic plant taxa have long represented a critical reservoir of ethnomedicinal resources, contributing substantially to the evolution and continuity of traditional healthcare practices (Abat, *et al.* 2017).

The use of ethnomedicinal floras can be traced to prehistoric periods and continues to play a significant role in both traditional and modern systems of medicine globally (World Health Organization, 2019). In the present study area, local communities rely extensively on plant species available in their immediate environment for the management of various febrile illnesses, including malaria, typhoid, dengue, chronic fever, and viral fever (World Health Organization, 2023). Knowledge pertaining to the identification, preparation, and therapeutic application of these medicinal plants is predominantly transmitted through oral traditions across generation (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization 2003). Herbal-based traditional medicine continues to constitute a fundamental component of primary healthcare rural regions India, where plant-derived remedies are widely utilized owing to their perceived therapeutic efficacy, affordability, accessibility, and strong cultural acceptance (Singh and Singh, 2009).

In India, ethnobotanical investigation have been extensively conducted by several workers, including Chopra, *et al.* (1956), Jain and Rao (1976), Jain (1991), Dastur (1996), Kirtikar and Basu (1999), Dubey, *et al.* (2004), and Bajpai, *et al.* (2016), thereby significantly enriching the documentation and systematization of indigenous plant-based knowledge. Within Uttar Pradesh, region-specific ethnobotanical assessments have also been conducted by numerous researchers, notably Singh and Maheshwari (1989), Pandey and Verma (2002), Singh, *et al.* (2002), Khanna (2002), Kumar, *et al.* (2003), Singh, *et al.* (2007), Dubey (2012), Kumar *et al.* (2013), Narayan and Singh (2017), Srivastava and Shukla (2018), Prajapati, *et al.* (2025) and Prajapati, *et al.* (2025).

Despite these contributions, ethnomedicinal knowledge in several localities remains inadequately documented. The present study aims to record and documentation of the traditional medicinal practices of ethnic communities in the study area, with the objective of conserving centuries-old indigenous knowledge for future generations and providing a scientific basis for further pharmacological investigations.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study area

Sohelwa Wildlife Sanctuary is located in the districts of Shravasti, Balrampur, and Gonda in the state of Uttar Pradesh, India, and extends along the Indo-Nepal international boundary. Geographically, it extends between 27°30'01" N and 27°55'42" N latitude and 81°55'36" E to 82°48'33" E longitudes (Forest Survey of India, 2021). Historically, the forest tract formed part of the Balrampur Estate and remained under the ownership of the Maharaja of Balrampur prior to the implementation of the Zamindari Abolition Act of 1952 (District Gazetteer, Gonda (1988). Subsequently, in 1988, the area was formally notified as a wildlife sanctuary to ensure the protection and management of its biological resources (Forest Survey of India, 2021). It covers approximately 452 km² and extends as a narrow east–west corridor about 120 km in length and 6–8 km in width along the Indo–Nepal international border. Sohelwa Wildlife Sanctuary constitutes an important component of the Bhabar–Terai ecosystem, a biogeographic zone recognized for its high biodiversity and ecological significance (Champion *et al.* 1968).

The vegetation of the sanctuary is characterized by a mosaic of deciduous and semi-evergreen forest types (Forest Survey of India, 2021). The floral composition is dominated by species such as *Shorea robusta* (Sal), *Tectona grandis* (Teak), *Terminalia bellirica* (Bahera), *Anogeissus latifolia* (Phaldu), *Syzygium cumini* (Jamun), *Dalbergia sissoo* (Shisham), *Grewia tiliifolia* (Dhamina), *Lannea coromandelica* (Jigna), *Adina cordifolia* (Haldu), *Terminalia tomentosa* (Asna), and *Acacia catechu* (Khair). The sanctuary supports diverse faunal assemblages and provides important habitats for several wildlife species typical of the Terai region (Champion, *et al.*, 1968 and Rodgers *et al.*, 2002). The surrounding landscape has traditionally been inhabited by tribal community, whose livelihood practices have historically been linked with forest resources (Champion, *et al.*, 1968).

Figure 1. Geographical location of the Sohelwa Wildlife Sanctuary and its adjoining areas.

2.2. Ethnobotanical survey, identification and documentation

Field trips were systematically conducted in the Sohelwa Wildlife Sanctuary and its adjoining areas of the Tarai region to collect plant specimens from various locations across different seasons. The Tharu community and other local inhabitants assisted in identifying plants based on their traditional uses. During collection, detailed notes were recorded in a notebook, including the collection number, local name, accepted scientific name, family, vegetation type, and photographs of each specimen. Specimens were carefully processed, preserved, and poisoned using Mercuric Chloride (HgCl_2) to prevent fungal and insect damage. They were then mounted on standard herbarium sheets (41×28 cm), with labels documenting essential information such as the botanical name, family, habitat, location, collector's name, collection number, and other relevant details necessary for accurate identification (Jain and Rao, 1977). Identification of specimens was carried out using standard reference books and floras, including Hooker (1872–1897) and Duthie (1960). The prepared herbarium specimens were subsequently deposited in the Department of Botany, Prof. B. K. Verma Herbarium, Maharaja Bijli Pasi Government P.G. College, Lucknow of Uttar Pradesh.

Figure 2. Photograph showing the interaction among the rural communities of Sohelwa Wildlife Sanctuary and its adjoining areas.

2.3. Data Collection

To systematically documentation of the ethnomedicinal plants of the Sohelwa Wildlife Sanctuary and its adjoining areas used in the management of various types of febrile illnesses, an extensive field survey was conducted from December 2024 to February 2026. Primary information was obtained from traditional healers, particularly elderly members of the Tharu tribes and other local inhabitants, who possess extensive knowledge of plant uses. Data collection involved a pretested questionnaire (format provided in the supplementary information), direct field observations, and structured interviews. Detailed information on methods of preparation, modes of consumption, shelf-life, and other ethnobotanical practices was gathered through discussions with traditional healers, knowledgeable community members, and local Vaidyas of the tribal community.

3. Results

3.1. Demographic feature of the informants

An extensive ethnobotanical survey was conducted in the Sohelwa Wildlife Sanctuary of the Tarai region, Uttar Pradesh, involving interviews with 80 local informants (Table 1). Among the respondents, 70 individuals (87.5%) were male and 10 individuals (12.5%) were female. The predominance of male participants may be attributed to their greater willingness to engage in discussions with interviewers, whereas female informants exhibited comparatively lower participation, likely due to sociocultural constraints. The informants comprised a diverse group, including traditional herbal practitioners, medicinal plant collectors, farmers, and herdsman. Traditional practitioners demonstrated substantial knowledge regarding the identification and utilization of indigenous medicinal plants for the treatment of various ailments.

The age distribution indicated that 24 participants (30%) were in the 50–59-year group, 43 participants (54%) were in the 60–70-year group, and 13 participants (16%) were above 70 years. This suggests that ethnomedicinal knowledge is predominantly retained among older individuals. Regarding

educational status, 69 informants (86%) were illiterate, while 11 (14%) had primary education. Illiterate respondents contributed more detailed information on traditional medicinal plant use than their literate counterparts. This may be associated with increasing reliance on modern healthcare systems, lifestyle changes, and gradual erosion of traditional knowledge due to urbanization.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of informants in Sohelwa Wildlife Sanctuary and its adjoining areas of the Tarai region, Uttar Pradesh.

Demographic Feature	Category	Number of Persons	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	70	87.5
	Female	10	12.5
Age (years)	50–59	24	30
	60–70	43	54
	>70	13	16
Education	Illiterate	69	86
	Primary	11	14
Total		80	100

Table 2. Documentation of various Herbal and Local plants used by local inhabitants of Sohelwa Wildlife Sanctuary and its adjoining areas.

S. No.	Botanical Name	Local Name	Family	Febrile illnesses	Part uses
1.	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Corr.	Bel	Rutaceae	Typhoid, Fever	Bark, Leaves
2.	<i>Allium sativum</i> L.	Lahsun	Liliaceae	Fever	Bulb
3.	<i>Aloe barbadensis</i> Mill.	Gheekumar	Liliaceae	Fever	Leaves
4.	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i> (L.) R. Br.	Chhatian	Apocynaceae	Malaria fever and fever	Bark
5.	<i>Alysicarpus pupleurifolius</i> (L.) DC.	Akranti	Fabaceae	Fever	Whole plant
6.	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Burm. f.) Wall.	Chirata	Acanthaceae	Malaria fever and fever	Whole plant
7.	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Chirchita	Amaranthaceae	Malaria fever	Whole
8.	<i>Anthocephalus chinensis</i> (Lamk.) Rich. Ex Walp.	Kadam	Rubiaceae	Fever	Bark
9.	<i>Argemone maxicana</i> L.	Pili Katari	Papaveraceae	Malaria fever	Root
10.	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> Juss.	Neem	Meliaceae	Typhoid, Malaria fever	Leaves, Bark
11.	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i> (L.) Penn.	Bramhi, Jalnaveri	Scrophulariaceae	Fever	Whole plant
12.	<i>Bauhinia variegata</i> L.	Kachnar	Fabaceae	Malaria fever	Bark
13.	<i>Boerhaavia diffusa</i> L.	Patharchatta	Nyctaginaceae	Malaria	Root

			ae	fever	
14.	<i>Blumea lacera</i> (Burm. f.) DC.	Purroh	Asteraceae	Fever	Whole plant
15.	<i>Bombax ceiba</i> L.	Semal	Malvaceae	Fever	Bark
16.	<i>Caesalpinia bonduca</i> (L.) Roxb.	Karanj	Fabaceae	Fever	Seed
17.	<i>Calotropis procera</i> Br.	Madar	Asclepiadaceae	Fever	Root
18.	<i>Carica papaya</i> L.	Papita	Caricaceae	Dengue	Leaves
19.	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i> L.	Patha	Menispermaceae	Typhoid fever	Root
20.	<i>Clerodendrum serratum</i> (L.) Moon.	Bharang	Verbenaceae	Malaria fever	Root
21.	<i>Clerodendrum viscosum</i> Vent.	Bhatwasi, Addakajo	Verbenaceae	Fever, Malaria fever	Leaves
22.	<i>Cuscuta capitata</i> Roxb.	Deelasazin	Convolvulaceae	Fever	Whole Plant
23.	<i>Datura metel</i> L.	Dhatura	Solanaceae	Fever	Fruit
24.	<i>Evolvulus alsinoides</i> (L.) L.	Chatpatia	Convolvulaceae	Fever	Root
25.	<i>Ficus bengalensis</i> L.	Bargad	Moraceae	Fever	Bark
26.	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L.	Piple	Moraceae	Typhoid fever	Bark
27.	<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i> L.	Betjongnaro	Malvaceae	Fever	Flower
28.	<i>Justicia adhatoda</i> L.	Adusa	Acanthaceae	Typhoids	Leaves
29.	<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	Galphusia	Verbenaceae	Malaria	Stem
30.	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Aam, Amba	Anacardiaceae	Fever	Leaves
31.	<i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	Karela	Cucurbitaceae	Malaria fever	Leaves
32.	<i>Momordica dioica</i> Roxb.	Bankarela	Cucurbitaceae	Fever	Root
33.	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.	Saijana	Moringaceae	Fever	Bark
34.	<i>Nyctanthes arbor-tristis</i> L.	Gargad, Harsingar	Oleaceae	Malaria fever	Leaves
35.	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i> L.	Babri-biol, tulsi	Lamiaceae	Dengue, Malaria fever	Leaves
36.	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i> L.	Amrul	Oxalidaceae	Fever	Leaves, Whole plant
37.	<i>Rauvolfia serpentina</i> (L.) Benth. ex Kurz.	Sarpagandha	Apocynaceae	Malaria fever	Root
38.	<i>Sida cordifolia</i> L.	Bala	Malvaceae	Malaria fever	Root
39.	<i>Solanum melongena</i> var. <i>incanum</i> (L.) Ktze.	Banbhantawa	Solanaceae	Fever	Fruits
40.	<i>Solanum nigrum</i> L.	Bhambhola	Solanaceae	Fever	Fruits
41.	<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i> DC.	Dudoribon	Asteraceae	Fever	Whole plant
42.	<i>Tabernaemontana divaricata</i> (L.) Br. ex Roem. & Schult.	Chandni	Apocynaceae	Fever	Leaves
43.	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.	Amli, Imli	Fabaceae	Fever	Leaves

44.	<i>Terminalia alata</i> Roxb.	Asan	Combretaceae	Fever	Bark
45.	<i>Tinospora codifolia</i> (L.) Merr.	Athervel, Giloe	Menispermaceae	Dengue, Fever	Whole plant
46.	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> L.	Bellamaku	Asteraceae	Fever	Roots
47.	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i> L.	Lapetua, Adasisi	Asteraceae	Malaria fever	Leaves
48.	<i>Uraria picta</i> (Jacq.) Desv.	Pitvan	Fabaceae	Fever	Root

3.2. Diversity of medicinal plants use

The ethnobotanical assessment documented a diverse assemblage of 48 medicinal plant species, distributed across 44 genera and 27 families, which are traditionally employed in the management of various febrile disorders. The substantial taxonomic diversity observed in this study reflects the depth and richness of traditional knowledge systems related to fever management within the study area.

Among the recorded families, Fabaceae was the most dominant, contributing five species, followed by Asteraceae, which was represented by four species. Apocynaceae, Malvaceae, Solanaceae, and Verbenaceae each contributed three species. Furthermore, Acanthaceae, Convolvulaceae, Cucurbitaceae, Liliaceae, Menispermaceae and Moraceae were represented by two species each. The remaining families such as Rutaceae, Amaranthaceae, Rubiaceae, Papaveraceae, Meliaceae, Scrophulariaceae, Nyctaginaceae, Asclepiadaceae, Anacardiaceae, Moringaceae, Oleaceae, Lamiaceae, Oxalidaceae, Combretaceae, Caricaceae and Fabaceae were each represented by a single species.

Figure 3. Major plant families used in ethnomedicine in the Sohelwa Wildlife Sanctuary and adjacent areas.

3.3. Number of medicinal plants used for febrile illnesses

A total of 30 plant species were recorded in the study area for the treatment of fever. Additionally, 15 species were reported to be used in the management of malaria, while 5 species were identified for the treatment of typhoid and 3 species for dengue fever. These findings underscore the diversity of medicinal plant species utilized locally for the management of febrile and infectious diseases.

Figure 4. Ethnomedicinal plants used for different types of febrile illnesses in Sohelwa Wildlife Sanctuary and adjoining areas.

3.4. Number of medicinal plant parts used in the treatment of febrile illnesses

In the study area, a variety of plant parts were reported for the treatment of fever, reflecting diverse ethnomedicinal practices. Leaves were the most commonly utilized plants part, recorded in 14 species. Roots were used in 11 species, followed by bark in 10 species and whole plants in 9 species. The use of fruits was comparatively limited, being reported in only 2 species. Seeds and flowers were the least utilized plant parts, each recorded in a single species. This distribution indicates a clear preference for vegetative plant parts in traditional fever remedies.

Figure 5. Plants part used in different types of febrile illnesses in Sohelwa Wildlife Sanctuary and adjoining areas.

4. Discussion

The predominance of families such as Fabaceae and Asteraceae is consistent with previous ethnobotanical investigations and may be attributed to their wide distribution and rich phytochemical profiles, including compounds with documented antipyretic, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties. The representation of numerous families by one or two species further indicates a diversified and adaptive ethnomedicinal framework, likely developed to address a range of fever aetiologies. These findings underscore the importance of preserving traditional medicinal knowledge and highlight the potential of the documented plant species for future pharmacological and phytochemical investigations.

Conclusion:

The present study documents the ethnomedicinal use of plant resources in the Sohelwa Wildlife Sanctuary and adjoining areas of the Tarai region of Uttar Pradesh, revealing significant floristic diversity utilized in the treatment of febrile illnesses. A total of 48 plant species belonging to 44 genera and 27 families were recorded, indicating the continued dependence of local communities on traditional plant based healthcare. The predominance of Fabaceae and Asteraceae reflects their ecological abundance and medicinal relevance in the region.

Traditional knowledge was found to be largely confined to elderly informants, suggesting a gradual decline in intergenerational knowledge transmission due to modernization and increased reliance on allopathic medicine. Leaves and roots were the most frequently used plant parts, highlighting their accessibility and perceived therapeutic efficacy. The documented species provide valuable leads for future phytochemical and pharmacological investigation. Preservation of both medicinal plant

diversity and associated traditional knowledge in therefore, essential for sustaining indigenous healthcare practices and biodiversity conservation.

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